

The Effect of Listening Shadowing on Iranian Elementary EFL Learners' Grammar Achievement

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ABSTRACT

The most important part of learning and teaching a foreign language is its grammar. It is regarded that grammar is the most significant feature of language for not only learning but also teaching. The present study investigated the effects of shadowing on grammar achievement of Iranian elementary learners. To attain the purpose of the study, 40 Iranian elementary female learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students were selected. They were 12 to 16 years old. The participants were assigned to two experimental groups: listening-based shadowing group and a control group. During the treatment period, the control group underwent traditional instruction. However, the experimental groups were instructed using shadowing. The results revealed that listening based shadowing had a significant effect on learners' grammar achievement. The results indicated that there was a significant difference between listening-based group and the control group in the grammar achievement. The findings are applicable in pedagogy context as well as for further research.

Keywords: Listening, Shadowing, Iranian, Grammar Achievement

Introduction

The most important part of learning and teaching a foreign language is its grammar. It is regarded that grammar is the most significant feature of language for not only learning but also teaching. Crystal (1967) states that, "Grammar is the study of all the contrasts of meaning that it is possible to make within sentences" (p.32). Richards (2002) define grammar "as a description of the structure of a language and the way in which linguistic units such as words and phrases are combined to produce sentences in a language" (p.251).

There are different ways to help EFL learners to learn different parts of language. The role of EFL teachers in this regard could not be ignored. In the process of learning a foreign language, similar to the first language, the learners need someone and some methods to imitate to learn new materials and different teachers have tried different approaches of and techniques so far. Shadowing, as an example, is a language learning technique. This technique means "learners attempt to repeat--to 'shadow' -- what they hear as quickly and accurately as they hear it" (Wang, 2017, p.196). Ye (1983) believes that in the shadowing technique, the learners need to speak while listening and they should try to keep up with the speed of the recording, almost making the sounds at the same time. Lambert (1991) asserts that "shadowing exercise technically is a rhythmic acoustic tracking task that requires the practicer to make instant sounds to the sound stimulus signal" (p.590).

The significance of the present study lies in a number of areas. First of all, to the researcher's knowledge, there are not many studies that have been conducted in order to explore the influence of using shadowing on grammar learning of language learners and tries to find the significant impact of having exposure to the shadowing practices. It can also help the theorician in this field to understand the learning process better. The results can be important to teacher trainers as they can introduce the technique to the novice or in service teachers. Accordingly, teachers may use shadowing practice to help learners to learn grammar. Instructors could use shadowing as a way to encourage their learners to become proficient in different parts of learning a language. The result of present study could be of considerable importance for learners since shadowing is the process of paying attention to spoken or written language and repeat it as fast as possible.

Therefore, as grammar teaching and learning is important in language courses and as it is necessary to test new ways to teach it, this study has been conducted. With regard to the inadequate studies on using shadowing to improve grammar, the researcher decided to study the effect of using shadowing on grammar learning.

The aim of this study is to help the teacher to find new ways to teach grammar implicitly in EFL classes. The results of this research could essentially provide insights into the improvement of Iranian EFL Learners language proficiency. It is expected that the obtained results from this research give some recommendation about the improvement of EFL learners' grammatical competence. The future researchers can use these results to make their educational contexts more interactive and interesting.

To explore the importance of shadowing in language learning the main aim of the present study was to investigate the influence of listening based shadowing on Iranian elementary EFL learners' grammar achievement.

Methodology

This study was conducted in true-experimental mode since the participants were randomly assigned to different groups. The independent variable of this study is shadowing, and the dependent variable of the study is grammar learning.

3.3 Participants

The participants of this study were 40 elementary EFL learners. The participants were females learning English as a foreign language in a language institute, aged 12-16. The researcher used the available sampling method in this study. They were randomly assigned to two groups, experimental and control group.

3.4 Instruments

There was an instrument in the present study:

3.4.1 Test of Grammar

The next instrument of the present study was a pretest and posttest of grammar knowledge. It was a researcher made test that included 35 multiple-choice tests. This test contained multiple-choice tests on verbs (simple present and present continuous). The criterion for the scoring procedure was one mark for each correct answer. The reliability of this test was estimated using Kr-21 formula and it was 0.85. To insure the content validity of this test, the researchers asked some experts to insure the content validity of this test. The test was administered to all of the participants to measure their knowledge of English grammar. After the treatment, this test was given to the participants as the posttest to determine the effect of treatment on the participants of the experimental groups.

3.5 Procedure

This study lasted for ten weeks. To conduct this study, the researcher chose sixty Iranian elementary learners and assigned them into two different groups. At the first session and to measure learners' grammar knowledge, the researcher used a grammar test as the pre-test. The results of the pretests revealed that at the beginning of the study, the participants of all of the groups were at the same level of proficiency in grammar knowledge. The first group was control group; the second group was an experimental group (listening-based group). The listening-based group received listening-based shadowing. For this group, the researcher presented the sentences to the learners auditory and asked them to repeat the sentences. In listening-based shadowing technique learners should listen to grammar text in the target language and then repeat it aloud. At the end of the treatment phase and to investigate the effect of treatment, the researcher used the grammar test again as posttest. The results of pre-tests and posttests were compared to find the effect of the treatment on the experimental groups.

3.6 Data Analysis

To analyze the obtained data from the grammar test and to assess the effect of treatment on the participants of the experimental groups, a set of descriptive and inferential statistics have been performed. To assess the normality of the data of pretests and posttests, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test was performed. The researcher used ANCOVA test to compare the results of the pretests and posttests. All of the stages of data analysis have been done using SPSS 21.00.

Results

Examining the Normality of Data

Before performing the analysis of data, normality of collected data was assessed using One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. This test was used to show the normality of distribution of data and to make decision about using parametric or nonparametric test to analyze data. In this statistics test, when significance is less than 0.05, the distribution of data is not normal and it is not possible to use parametric tests. When significance is more than 0.05, the distribution of data is normal and it is possible to use parametric tests. The results of this test are reported in Table 1.

Table 1

One-Sample Kolmogorov- Smirnow Test of Pretests and Posttests of Grammar Test

		Grammar pretest	Grammar posttest
N		60	60
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	12.816	21.150
	Std. Deviation	4.738	8.106
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.133	.131
	Positive	.133	.088
	Negative	-.130	-.131
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.027	1.018
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.242	.251

a. Test distribution is Normal.

Table 1 shows the results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test of pretests and posttests of grammar test. The results showed that the data of all of the tests are normal, because for all of the variables significance was more than 0.05. Accordingly, it was possible to use parametric tests to analyze data.

Addressing the Research Question

The research question of the present study was: Does listening-based shadowing significantly improve Iranian elementary EFL learners’ grammar achievement?

To answer this research question, and to find the effect of listening based shadowing on grammar learning of the participants of the listening based experimental group, a set of descriptive statistic was performed. The results are reported in the following Table.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of Pretests of grammar of the Control and Listening Based Experimental Groups

	group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Grammar Pretest	control	20	12.85	5.25
	listening group	20	13.10	4.29

Table 2 shows the mean, standard deviation, and standard error mean. As it is obvious from this Table, the mean score of pretest of the control and listening based experimental groups are 12.85 and 13.10, respectively. This Table also indicates that the standard deviation of pretests of the control and listening

based experimental groups are 5.25 and 4.29, respectively. It seems that there are no significant differences between the mean scores of both groups in grammar pretests. The next Table shows the descriptive statistics of grammar posttests of both groups.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics of Posttests of grammar of the Control and Listening Based Experimental Groups

group2	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
control	13.10	5.00	20
listening group	27.90	4.87	20
Total	20.50	8.94	40

According to the above Table, the mean score of the control and listening based experimental groups are 13.10 and 27.90 respectively. The standard deviation of the control and experimental groups are 5.00 and 4.87, respectively. The results revealed that the mean score of grammar of the listening based experimental group is higher than the control group.

To find the effect of listening based shadowing on grammar learning of the listening based experimental group, an ANCOVA test was performed to compare the mean scores of posttests of grammar of the experimental and control groups. The next Table shows the results of this test.

Table 4

ANCOVA Test of Mean Scores of Grammar of Listening Based Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^b
Corrected Model	2887.12	2	1.44	2.31	.000	.926	4.62	1.000
Intercept	365.5	1	365.56	5.85	.000	.613	58.58	1.000
Grammar pretest listening based group2	696.7	1	696.72	1.11	.000	.751	1.11	1.000
Error	2123.3	1	2.12	3.40	.000	.902	3.40	1.000
Error	230.8	37	6.24					
Total	19928.0	40						
Corrected Total	3118.0	39						

The result of the ANCOVA test shows that the obtained Sig is 0.00 which is lower than 0.05. According to the results of this test, there is a significant difference between the mean scores of posttests of grammar in the control and listening based experimental groups. The results revealed that using listening based

shadowing had a significant effect on learners' grammar learning. To find out whether this difference is statistically difference, with the assumption of homogeneity of variances, pairwise comparison using Bonferroni test was made between the two groups. The results of this test are reported in the next table.

Table 5

Pairwise Comparison of the Reading Based Experimental and Control Group

(I) group2	(J) group2	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
control	listening group	-14.57*	.790	.000	-16.17	-12.97
listening group	control	14.57*	.790	.000	12.97	16.17

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

According to the above table, the mean difference of the listening based experimental group and the control group is -14.57 and the sig<0.05. It shows that the mean scores of the listening based experimental group were significantly higher than the control group. In other words listening based shadowing had a significant effect on learners' grammar achievement.

Conclusion

No study has been done on the effect of shadowing on grammar achievement but some researchers conducted studies on the effect of shadowing on learners' different skills and different aspects of language learning and the results of their studies are in line with the results of the present research. In this regard, the results of the present study were in line with Hamada (2011, 2012), Yonezava and Ware (2008), Sumarish (2017). These researchers concluded that using shadowing has a significant effect on learners' listening skill. The findings of this research also in tandem with Wang (2017), Omar and Umehara (2010), Yavari and Shafiee (2019), Azimi and Ghanbari (2012), and Zakari (2014) who found out that using shadowing has a significant effect on learners' speaking and oral performance. The results are also correlate with Hamada (2015), Nakanishi and Ueda (2011), Suzuki (2007), Shiki, Mori, Kadota, and Yoshida (2010), and Willardson (2014). They studied the effect of shadowing on language proficiency and the results of their study indicated the significant effect of shadowing on students' language proficiency.

It is a very long time that EFL teachers are looking for effective ways to help their students to achieve grammar easily. Shadowing has been used as a tool for language learning. In most of the language classes, teachers use traditional and explicit ways to teach grammar. Shadowing, however, is a well-established activity which is somewhat different from the traditional methods that teachers use in the classes .

The results of this study demonstrated the usefulness of shadowing for grammar learning. Based on the data analysis in the previous chapter and result and discussions of this research, the researcher has concluded several points as follow. The results indicated that elementary learners' grammar learning improves after they have been used shadowing technique. It was proven by the data shown. The mean or the average score of grammar posttest of the participants of the reading based and listening based experimental group were higher than those of the control group and the students of the experimental groups got a better result in grammar test. This finding implies that using shadowing is a good way to help learners to improve their grammar knowledge. Therefore, it seems that using shadowing is a good approach to help learners to learn grammar and consequently improve their language proficiency level.

The results also showed that the participants of the listening based shadowing group had better performance than the participants of the reading based group. The findings indicated that there is a significant difference between the scores of the participants of reading based and listening based group and the participants of the listening based group outperformed the participants of the reading based group.

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